

An Analysis of the Moral–Religious Values in the U.S.A. and Europe from a Sociological Perspective

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ABSTRACT: This paper serves as a sketchy comparative analysis of religious values from the perspectives of European and American cultures. Using the sociological method, the author presents a trend analysis of the role that religious and moral values play in the private and public life. Because values are rooted in their substrate and social change, the sociological positivist theory of classic transition is analyzed in its relationship with the trend of relativism. They highlight the living conditions and interests, as they meet in the nodal point of legal positivism.

KEY WORDS: society, religion, values, moral

Introduction

James Vander Zanden once wrote that “conceptions values ensure that we assess people, objects and events, and we appreciate their importance based on merit, beauty or morality. We appeal to values in some instances the ultimate rational for the choices we make in life.”¹ With these words in mind and through the lenses of sociology, this paper will analyze the moral–religious values as defined and understood in the United States of America and in Europe.

The role of religion in the contemporary society has become increasingly significant particularly in USA, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Indonesia and Pakistan. A quick reading of Fig. 1, will be convincing enough to notice that Christianity, Islam and Hinduism,² are large enough to manifest a strong influence in the public life. These are the main religions that reshape the values in contemporary society and the best example in this case is the revitalization of religion in India. While Hindu nationalism led to some distancing between Hindus and non-Hindus (e.g., Christians, Muslims, and others), in Pakistan Islamization of the civil society has made inroads during the last four or five decades; as governments and regular citizens try to reassert Islamic identity. The impact of such religious activity led to the marginalization of religions that had smaller number of members.

Fig. 1. The graph great religions in the contemporary world

In Sri Lanka, the politicization of Buddhism had already taken place for some time—the Buddhist monks playing an active role in the government and holding political positions—and this led to a sense of political confusion and antagonism.

In Israel, one can see a similar pattern, where one can argue that Judaism had been somewhat distorted as it had been hijacked by violent organizations. The militarization of the Zionist movement led to the marginalization of various religious (Muslim and Christian), and ethnic minorities (Palestinians).

In a different way, religious fervor is noticeable also in the United States of America, where the Christian right is defused into a struggle against international terrorism, immigration and Islam.³

1) Contemporary Religious Moral Values in the United States

The US culture is a Western culture that originally emerged from the European culture, and had developed on its own trajectory since long before the US became an independent country with its own unique social and cultural characteristics such as dialect, music, arts, social customs, cuisine and folklore. Today, the U.S. is an ethnically and racially diverse country with a mosaic of multiculturalism generated by a widespread immigration from many different countries throughout its history.

Fig. 2. Religious affiliation and religious guidelines contemporary U. S. A.⁴

Religion in the United States is characterized by great diversity in both religious beliefs and practices (Figure 2) and a high level of religious participations. Numerous Americans consider the role of religion in their lives as being “very important.” A modern poll indicates that 83% of Americans say they belong to a religious denomination, 40% say they attend religious services every week, and 58% pray every week.⁵ Whether we are talking about the north or the south, over 50% affirm that religion is an important factor in addressing contemporary values. However, despite this level of apparent religiosity, according to a 2008 survey, only 9% of Americans stated that religion was the most important aspect of their lives, compared with 45% who stated that religion was very important in the life of their family, and 17% who made very important section: *money and career*.⁶

Faith in God | Various surveys were conducted to determine the beliefs Americans about the God of the 899 adults surveyed, 76% expressed their belief in God, 9% believe in a spirit or a universal power, 8% do not believe in anything, and 1% did not know. A 2008 study on 1,000 people concluded that, based on their beliefs, rather than on identifying their religion, 70% of Americans believe in a personal God, about 12% of Americans are atheists or agnostics, and other 12% are deist.⁷

Fig. 3. Religious Orientations/Religious Traditions in the United States⁸

The survey was conducted nationwide on a representative sample of 2502 US citizens (over 18), in 2006. The survey included two over-samples: 250 Hispanic and 250 African Americans. It was the deepest survey on religion, values, policies, etc., among North Americans. The approach was based on the methodology developed by political scientist John Green, who made a composite called “religious factor”. It managed to identify certain issues relating to religious values: religious orientation, matters of faith, Bible study, prayer, religious behaviors, importance of religion, etc.

A major finding in the study showed that most Americans believe that the *moral-religious values in America are weaker* than they were 20 years ago. Most Americans attribute moral decline to Mass Media. National Cultural Values Study found that 68% of Americans say that the media - entertainment and news - have a negative effect on moral values in America. In addition, 74% believe that moral values are weaker due to the direct influence of media,

which is the second largest factor influencing moral and religious value after parents and families.⁹

Lower standards of sexuality are another factor to decrease in value, 16% believe that sex between unmarried adult is not indicated, 49% say it depends on the situation, 65% excuses sex outside of marriage, and 45% believe that divorce can be offered anytime and for any reason. Only 67% believe that premarital sex among high school students is something bad, 49% believe that homosexuality is wrong.

Another major finding is that *America lost the fear of God*, only 52% believe that the Bible is the Word of God and has authority, 36% believe we should live by God's principles; 15% live according to their personal principles and 45% prefer to combine the teachings of God with their own values.

Also, *lost their perception of good and evil*, in other words, 53% are willing to tolerate assisted suicide, 28% are willing to exclude religious principles from government. No young people do not have the correct perception of good and evil, even among students observing major decline among religious moral values and standards.

The study shows very clearly that America's cultural decline is due to the remoteness of God's principles. Despite the decline in moral Americans still believe in the virtues of classic 51% believe that lying is not good in any situation, 46% say that you have to your promises in any case, 31% are willing to break the law, while 65% say it is wrong always, 57% would not deceive partner and 25% would accept illegal drugs. Institute for Culture and Media is a division of the Centre for Research and Media founded in October 2006 to expose media campaigns against traditional values and help restore America's cultural.¹⁰

2) Religious Moral Values in Contemporary Europe

When it comes to contemporary culture, it is very difficult to define a dominant trend that might come off during this period. If in the past, they could find notions Ages or romance or socialism, the

contemporary period bears no mark of a stream which can be defined in one word, although many researchers have tried names like hedonism, individualism, ego-society. At this stage the values are very different, they have evolved and morphed over time, it is sometimes difficult to assign a name abstract concrete, as was done in the past.

Prevailing value systems are treated with indifference and grows increasingly struggle between the keepers of values and their innovators. In a crisis of education, comes a new form of communication between generations, the younger generation refuses authority of the older generation, are widening gaps in communication and the communication between generations actual values becomes an impossibility. In this respect, the values of the older, fade and do not go to the young, because the younger generation aspires to other values, in another life.

1. Scientific thinking	2. Love	3. Reasoning (thought)	4. Individual autonomy	5. Emancipation from religion
Promethean spirit Beauty Body and sport Sense State The idea of law	Person Dignity Justice Happiness Honesty Respect Hospitality Fidelity Brotherhood Goodwill The spirit of self-help	Democracy Intelligence Training Knowledge Time (measured) Work	Relativism Pluralism Tolerance	Critical Spirit Progress Entrepreneurship Efficacy Saving and investment Money
6. Reason (instrumentality)	7. Utilities	8. The Right of peoples to self-determination	9. Leisure Activities	10. Family
Human rights Freedom of conscience Separation of church and state Happiness	Welfare Consumption Private property Market Competition Technology Social justice Solidarity Equality Social security	Peace Debt intervention	Women's Empowerment Nature Protection	

Table.1. European contemporary values¹¹

Also, the general media provides a powerful channel of circulation values, where the spread of the contraceptive pill is one of the major conditions for abolishing the taboos on sex.

Reborn in the void of history manufacturers values of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, socialist liberal sociologists, anthropologists, some emphasizing traditional values and giving them new forms of expression, most however, giving them an advantage over those “new” specific weather contemporary.

Also, the transmitters of values (journalists, artists, writers, actors, professors, priests) spreading the values and ideas of producers. But innovative role is confirmed well that I had in the field of clerics. *Perhaps it is best equipped in terms of cultural criticism to a given situation and determine to change that.*¹²

Scientize noteworthy social progress and becoming more obvious the twentieth century, we must admit that the modern era has its problems and failures. Ascension brings science cynicism and moral relativism; secularization of pathological creates tensions that lead to chaos and nihilism; selfishness and individualism encourages social alienation; democratization leads to the “revolt of the masses”, resulting in a culture of mediocrity and conformism. Contra-illuminist social ideology argues that the modern era requires a perpetual social crisis. It springs from impotence secular reason to create symbolic structures that give high values and thorough guidelines, which give our lives meaning and coherence.

Max Weber, in a deliberately turns expectations Millennium Enlightenment with the apocalyptic: “No one knows who will live in the future in this cage or if the end of this long process will not appear prophets entirely new, if not a spectacular rebirth of old ideas and ideals, or if we do not reach a petrified mechanization, perk up with a sort of spasmodic conceit. For about the last stage of this cultural developments we might as well say, rightly: specialists without spirit, sensualists heartless; this nullity imagines that they have reached a level of civilization never before never been touched.”¹³

Secularization is that which induces a cultural crisis, and it starts a modernization insufficient and misdirected. It also rejects the Enlightenment except that reason can help build a good society and rational. They tend, however, that religious revival to initiate

socio-cultural renewal. This comes in contrast badly with regard to religious practices in society.

Fig. 4. Variation religious practices in Europe (2010)

According to the indicators (Figure 4), Russia, Estonia, France, Iceland, Belarus or Ukraine, lies along the northern countries of Europe, the secular public in terms of religious practice. In these countries, less than 15% of the population attend church once a month, and religious behavior in public, was sharply reduced. In contrast, Bulgaria, Slovakia and Latvia recorded significant increases in public religious practice during this period. Regarding our country, its place is headed in Chapter religious practice. It is interesting that in Russia and the former Soviet states, which are predominantly Orthodox though, lies not with the Bulgaria or Romania, but they are the opposite.

Individualism is the characteristic of our epoch, the ego or selfishness prevailing at the expense of the community. This value new contemporary flavor, can be found in neo-liberalism or socialism, where abandoned collectivism. In general, individualism behaves like a manager and ask what personal rights: the right to be happy, the right to be respected, the right to be paid, the right to have a child or not, the right not to decide anything in my right without me to have a say.

Also, personal values outweighs the Institutional personal faith, marriage, etc.; personal happiness is more important than collective happiness. Psychological balance is very important, which is consulted psychiatrist or psychoanalyst, exposing that pathologies

dominant in our era no longer hysteria, but narcissism caused by a continuous search for self and favored techniques of analyzes of spirit as yoga, dynamics group, Zen, and other kinds of therapy.

Freedom, as a new form of search of self, ready for a new sensitivity that purpose in itself, a release of any constraint, distrust of attachments sustainable independence to the requirements of society, a free life, expressed in the saying: "It's my life, I'm free to do what I want when I want and how I want" (popular phrase).

Personal fulfillment is a manifestation of individualism, which is to feel good about yourself. Personal appearance is emphasized. Whether to be happy, have to contribute to the happiness of others, personal development means developing their own individual potential. You must not follow the predetermined rules, but must be yourself, aspirations and dreams. This accomplishment can take different forms: from professional fulfillment, social issues, a certain mental state, etc.

Everything can be sacrificed to become a man of success, though, Albert Einstein, in addition to the lessons that gives us the history and life, says: "It's not important to be a man of success but a man of value."¹⁴

Experimentation is the next logical aspect, in which the individual finds his own happiness, experiencing the solutions is offered, although they may be values or relevant solutions for himself and not for the community, so relative values. The multitude of value systems and conduct, created this relativism so that no one can claim to have found the solution or the truth, at most can claim the right to be different. Even in science, the notion of truth is very relative, because there are no facts, only interpretations. This relativism must also be tolerant, especially in the presence of others so personal experience becomes key to any election, including ethics or religion. Even the imposition of good and prohibiting evil become unacceptable, because you have to try, to experience it yourself alternatives and then draw their own conclusions (even promote religion in the United States shall: Try Jesus!/Tried for Jesus!).¹⁵ In this way, it makes the transition from a moral theory in a practical living.

Spontaneity, permissiveness, sexuality, intensity, hedonism and present time are linked because they interact, but it also presents a logical entity.

Spontaneity can be regarded as a value of a human guide postmodern and contemporary, it is free to seek their destiny, without an itinerary before stability. Cultivated still in school, spontaneity feeds imagination and creativity and enjoy tolerance, going so toward permissiveness.

International comparative surveys on European values (1981, 1990, 1999), which, in a particular matter have compiled a list of 22 acts (recourse to abortion, the practice of homosexuality, adultery, buying stolen goods, tax evasion, etc.) It shows that *permissiveness* is increasing in various fields, especially in matters of sexuality, and that France is among the most permissive countries.¹⁶ The desire to make the most of every moment in hand and search intensity is on the agenda and hence explosion to get involved in as many things, to travel more often and further, a cult of the body.

All these aspects form the other and hedonism, because pleasure is the one that dictates all the longings of the human body, immediate gratification, free of taboos, defendant, *carpe diem* (Romans)/Live for the moment! From 1980 to 2000, the prospect of this increase from 53.3% to 63.6%, and the prospect of future declines from 40.8% to 34.5% of respondents.

Conviviality, pairing spontaneity 60s was one of axial values, becoming a pipedream currently present in some circles, subgroups or societies showing values as: return to nature, simplicity, celebration, etc.

Ecology, or respect for nature, is an enduring value of this movement, increasing in proportion to the increase every age nuisances and industrial pollution.

Contemporary environmental issues, representing a danger for the survival and existence of life on this planet increasingly requires the intervention of ethics in their resolution. In the face of challenges of the contemporary era intelligence can stay accountable and humanism applied, not exhortation to pure virtue. Concerns and ideals of contemporary consciousness had to turn their attention to nature

*protection thus developing an environmental ethic that includes new values centered nature.*¹⁷

Equality is manifested on several levels: before the law, equal treatment of all citizens who are in the same situation, refusing privileges integrated morals. But in this case the value has evolved towards equality in opportunities. So, no matter what environment you what race you are, you have the same opportunities. All the activities that have been initiated to demand equality before the opportunities are part of the postmodern heritage. The value that looms behind these requirements is called “non-discrimination” and actions are called “positive discrimination”.

Duty | At the end of the twentieth century, there were naturally a number of protracted conflict situations, which manifests itself between moral duties and obligations. Equally naturally, as far as achieving parameters required for organizing a democratic modern type conflicts generally those between debt will subside and they, at least for the time required Assembly powers to pass or consumption and digestion of the victims, wealth fraudulently accrued etc.

Honesty | In the twentieth century, more and more philosophers, logicians and mathematicians have shown that the idea of truth epistemic is not so clear and understandable because, besides the fact that there are several conceptions of truth (the realistic truth-mail, outlook utilitarian-pragmatic, consensual theory etc.), each of which usually evolve to a more thorough explanation and richer in meaning.

Caution | Prudence implies uncertainty, risk, random, unknown. For this reason, and wisdom needs it because not a crazy wisdom. If science is a formal politeness, prudence is a real science to live and be happy, both now and in the future. It assures us that we must choose and what to avoid.

Courage | To understand courage must be started from an important distinction, that between its appearance psychological, sociological and moral. Psychosociologists declare that: the courage is a trait that is the lack of sensitivity to fear that, whether it is hardly felt, is well tolerated, sometimes with pleasure. For example, fans of dangerous missions, expeditions to the poles or on top of the world, lovers of scandal free with another band in the neighborhood,

are certainly courageous in psychological and sociological sense, but not moral. Courage becomes a value and a moral virtue only when it comes, at least in part, in the service of others; it shows that it was issued in a somewhat selfish interest immediately. To some extent, because I enunciation total is unlikely. Therefore, the recommendation Bible to love our neighbor as thyself refers, in fact, that selfishness educates issued by ego, which we also call generosity or even altruism. Seen thus, courage is present in any moral action as present and prudence, by the way.

Traditional values	Central values	Latent values	Postmodern values
Religion	Love	Justice	Individualism
Authority	Family	Solidarity	Fulfillment
Moral rigor	Friendship	Benevolence	Liberty
Obedience	Honesty	Kindness	Experimentation
Duty	Dignity		Relativity
Work	S u c c e s s f u l professional		Sincerity
Responsibility	Property		Tolerance
Fidelity	Consumerism		Spontaneity
	Safety		Permeability safety
	Leisure activities		Sexuality
	S c i e n c e / Technology		Intensity
	Progress		Hedonism
	Democracy		Present tense
	Peace		Conviviality

Table 2. Values at the beginning of XXI century¹⁸

Traditional Values | Traditions have not forgotten how to be, although they are always changing. Gradually, they conserve in some form, but not disappear from society. On the other hand, traditions change with society, even if changes are not ever as sudden or radical, as happens often with society.¹⁹

If we compare the new postmodern values, many of the old values prevalent for centuries, they have witnessed decline faster or slower. Whatever indicator is chosen, all over the world, it signaled

the decline of religion, faith understood as practical, action and behavior.

During the separation of religious institutions and faith generalize a list of ideas: the man has the right to create their own laws; It is not created, but is the result of an evolution, so it is perfectible; taking care of his journey on earth can eliminate all suffering and loneliness. God and man are starting to distance themselves, the latter having increasingly less need someone to explain the universe, to live or to find happiness. Society becomes secular: religion regulates them increasingly less rhythms, habits, celebrations, public space.

The next step would have been *authority* because it is representing the value of new values in whose name expansion is blocked. Even if it is the state authority in the family, at school, at work, she is known as oppressive, alienating. It is found everywhere not only by laws, the regulations in everyday relations between superiors and inferiors, etc.

Another step, is the *moral rigor* as representing the force which resists gains of freedom and permissiveness. There is nothing “old-fashioned” than to refer to ethical or “moral order.”

Obedience and duty are complementary values derive directly from the authority and moral rigor. As societies to function well, morality must be respected, and the man to fulfill his duty to obey authority.

Work represents an important value, but it is not synonymous with duty to the state and no longer represents a final value. It is linked to personal fulfillment, which determines the satisfactions of attorney. The work is not valued in any circumstance. Contemporary man wants as far as possible, be master of his own labor. Does not give the best of it unless its tasks are quite interesting, that if allow to be involved in the decisions and initiatives they take.

Responsibility is closely linked to freedom, and in the first phase, the current postmodern are not responsible. There can be no act that could be qualified as sin or mistake; there is only psychological processes that lead to certain behaviors determined that, in turn, causes disturbance, feelings of guilt, anxiety. These can be addressed

through a form of therapy or another and healed. Place of the priest in the confessional is taken by psychologists.

Fidelity knew a devaluation and later, a certain motion curing. Hat formerly held in high esteem because vital guarantee duration and soundness attachments. Must be entirely faithful to the homeland, family, political or ideological institutions superiors partner.

Fig. 5. Shared Religiosity in Europe (2010)

In the context of traditional values, according to data (Figure 5), we see that the average values of religiosity reach the maximum Malta, Poland, Ireland, showing a predominance of religious values and a low degree of secularization. In contrast, the data show very concrete idea of a profound secularization of societies Protestant majority and the preservation of religious values in societies predominantly Catholic (Denmark, Sweden). France (mostly Catholic) are among the champions of secularism and Bulgaria and Romania (predominantly Orthodox) is at the opposite pole.

If we look at Figure 5, grasp easily appearance of a phenomenon revitalization and effervescence of religion, especially in Eastern Europe, such as Bulgaria, Latvia, Slovakia, while secularism has advanced dramatically in countries like Ireland, Great Britain, Hungary spaces where religious values already lost more ground. It is also interesting to see that countries with such profound secularization, Denmark, Sweden or Finland, manifest religious effervescence during this period. Core values are present in the center of our culture and are subject to general agreement. Also,

crossing eras disorders and metamorphosis. May change in some ways, but not in their essential features.

Friendship is a value that prevails in our society fall within interpersonal, taking first place in the younger generation options, and for those who have little satisfaction in family life.

Love | As in Christianity, recognized the supreme value of any civilization, but specifically treated each of them is nuanced in our culture as the foundation of torque and marriage.

The category of moral values, *honor and dignity* are consistently considered the most important, although it can be manipulated through behavior inspired equivalent value, like racism or xenophobia.

In the economic sphere, the key value is the professional success because it is the foundation of social position and income that provides access to property and consumption. Most people put great weight on the concept of private property: my house, my car, my stuff.

Also, all the polls and surveys show that, regardless of space or time, the *family*, is the amount forefront, which is based on exclusive love of two people who founded a home.

Another central value in the life of contemporary society is the *consumerism*—offer endless objects and services offered with the choice, the pleasure of buying—is a value so striking that used to call “consumer society” corporate body promotes.²⁰

Although contemporary society tolerated substantially different forms of “deviance” and maintained *permissiveness*, especially in moral matters, reaffirms the need for security; a multidimensional value: safety in the face of crime and delinquency, the streets and public transport, work safety in the face of illness and various recurs of life.

Leisure activities are part of the consumer society, while procuring income and leisure, entertainment, travel, activities, multiple services. Even this value represents annual holidays in the most spectacular.

Desire for knowledge that characterizes civilization from its inception, continues to act and be manifested in particular by the value it synonymously ascribed to science and technology, whose

advances have spawned centuries idea of progress, is an increase of linear and uninterrupted humanity.

Together with *democracy* (supreme value among political values that citizens share and consider them as the foundation for human governance), peace has in turn become a central value (company's establishment of international peacekeeping in the world).²¹

Values: latent/hidden

The meaning of the good | In contemporary Western thought, good is conceived as something useful or something that answers a need or desire trends generating the resulting satisfaction. Although ethics is an obstacle to conquering human impulses, it proves to be very necessary to strengthen tendencies towards good and deliberate use of new media and particularly strong energy that mankind has for over half a century.

In the twentieth century, moral thinking, good and evil were considered permanent researchers, based on different assumptions. If utilitarianism believes that good or useful identify with what ensures maximum welfare, other thinkers argue that good as a simple property. Emerges as metaphysical values associated the knowledge like an interesting talking about intuition moral values: good as a property unnatural, which depends largely of individuals; good as an intrinsic value of human consciousness, which ensures dignity.

Justice, solidarity (fraternity), *benevolence* and mercy are shown in public speeches or edifying stories. However, they are poorly rated in surveys and rather placed last in the list than others. They are classified as "dormant" since he is present in a conscience dormant. They wake up when an unexpected event occurs when a situation is prolonged considered scandalous, or when a situation ends up causing a feeling of saturation. In these moments, may get a surprising and unexpected driving force.

Sense of justice against an oppressive system can induce a revolution. Solidarity can trigger when a disaster occurs. Indifference or hostility against a foreign group can turn into goodwill if from

this group exudes a commendable initiative. People can give up their own interests and if it finds kindness prove people poorer than them or that are suffering. New moves can be triggered from those motivations as “humanitarianism” or any other initiative to alleviate human suffering.

Justice | The new principle of justice does not invite tolerate injustice, but requests that she be tried and punished in such a way as to lead both to repair the spiritual and material, and the improvement of people’s consciousness to advance on the path of spiritual life more full.

Equity is a correlative value of justice, so, it is a more concrete form of moral justice, manifested in the human characters and not in actions to strengthen legal legality.

Logic and legal philosophy impressive contemporary informal insists that understanding and interpretation of legal laws to be made both in letter and in spirit (which is also moral). But the urge to judge fair is one of the main forms to be within the law. Because of this correlation justice with fairness, required two concepts of responsibility: legal and moral. It seems that just equity creates the most difficulties in explaining justice in two main forms of her social or distributive justice and corrective justice. Because it can turn into reality should be clear, however, that not only rights but also obligations must be specified. Also, it has developed a more complete theory of human needs, including the problem of hunger and poverty in the world today.

Duty | In Anglo-Saxon philosophy after World War II widened the debate over debt and obligations. If utilitarian argue that we need to follow as many consequences for good deontologists argue that we must pursue debts basic (gratitude, repair morality, loyalty, self-improvement, beneficence, not harming, justice), leaving room for supererogation (heroics and holiness).

Conflicts debt are factors of moral progress, some ethicists say. Others deny the existence of such conflicts, ranking it here and sociologist E. Durkheim. Debt moral conflicts manifest themselves very diverse. They can be: between socio-moral meanings of debts by profession, religion, political opinion, etc.; between old debts and new debts on the same type of legal or moral system; between

debt same moral agent, which forms part of various human groups: family, relatives, friends, group work, entertainment, research etc.

Can be conflicts between debt, on the one hand, and other values and moral virtues such as honor, dignity, kindness, honesty, modesty, courage, on the other hand.

Spirit of justice | Philosophers and writers such as Dostoevsky argued that if justice would disappear from the earth, that people continue to live would not have any value. Hence, it follows that justice had and will have an essential place in lists of values and moral virtues. Not coincidentally, it is considered that the best writings of moral philosophy of the twentieth century remain dedicated to justice.

The most ingenious and most common type of government the peoples of modern and contemporary society is democracy. Main lack of democracy was and remains that the less skilled get to decide in democratic bodies respectively in parliaments.

3) Developments and Religious Contrasts in Contemporary Europe

When we do an analysis of the former communist countries, we meet a fairly high degree of variability in terms of traditional religious cultures. In this space, we find countries where Orthodoxy predominates, as in Russia, Ukraine, Bulgaria, Belarus and Romania; countries with a strong Catholic tradition, such as Poland, Lithuania, Slovakia; traditionally Protestant countries, such as Estonia and East Germany; or multi-confessionals companies, such as Hungary, which also has a significant Protestant community, but also a strong Catholic tradition.

Everywhere in these countries, communism has attempted a forced removal of religion from the public and the private sectors and at the same time led a strong policy of atheism. But all policies against religion were different from state to state, as was different and the social impact of these policies.

Extremely important is the aspect that all European countries under the influence of Soviet power, religion was considered “the

opium of the peoples” and was one of the enemy’s main communist power, and throughout the twentieth century, communism, fought a fierce battle to weaken religious institutions and destruction of religious feelings among the population: were demolished and closed churches were imprisoned priests, the church was fenced involvement in public life has been drastically reduced religious education, religion was pushed to an area of increasingly anonymous “private nature of religion is in many cases daily experience of hundreds of millions in communist states.”²²

In these countries, secularization has emerged as a natural consequence of modernization, industrialization and promoting a pluralistic vision of the world, but it was forced product. However, secularization effects are felt much less in former communist countries than in Western Europe. Some researchers identify factors that influenced the degree of secularization in ex-communist countries, but each of them manifested differently from one area to another:²³

- The level of political repression against religion and against churches
- The modernization
- Dominant denomination
- Closer ties between religion and national ideas

Although there have been subordinated to political power and were transformed into departments of the communist state, the Orthodox Churches have kept a close link between Orthodoxy and national identity. So, for Romanian, Bulgarian, Serbian Orthodoxy has remained closely linked to national identity, its guarantor.²⁴

Czech Republic | In the countries of Central and Eastern Europe (East Germany, Czech Republic, Estonia), the secularization occurred amid a departure faithful to the Catholic Church, seen as an aggressor national identity and Protestantism was subjected to persecution by political power.

- 62% of Czechs do not belong to a church
- 8% frequently go to religious services
- 30% believe in God
- 17% believe in life after death

Estonia:

88% not apart to church

Latvia | In the Baltic countries (Latvia, Estonia, Lithuania), forced secularization effects were different in the three countries. In Lithuania (Catholicism) the level of religiosity remained high, despite atheism policy. In Latvia and Estonia (Lutheranism), the degree of secularization has skyrocketed due to industrialization and modernization, and religion began to play an increasingly reduced role.²⁵

64% do not belong to a church (in these countries the most religious population group is Russian.)

Hungary | In Hungary, the Catholic Church remained strong, but Protestantism was strongly affected so that the Catholic Church is still very large, while the Protestant lost many members.

42% of Hungarians say they do not belong to a particular church
30% have never belonged
14% go to Mass weekly
42% are Catholics

Bulgaria | Bulgaria (Orthodox majority) suffered after the fall of Communism. In the 90 Bulgarian Church was on the verge of a schism, because of clerical disputes.

Only 32% since membership into a religious (Orthodox Church)
5% attend religious services frequently
Only 7% say that God is important in their lives
The country's most permissive in terms of homosexuality, divorce, suicide, euthanasia, etc.

Poland is the most religious country in Central Europe. Poland (mostly Catholic) ranks first in Europe in terms of population religiosity, but also the influence of the Church in public life and politics. But religious extremism, antidemocratic, supported by some clergy and a number of legislative initiatives, the Church tried to impose by force (abortion), decreased popularity church.

66% of Polish people go to church every Sunday
 4% never go
 90% consider themselves religious
 Paradoxically, only 45% have faith in the church

	homosexuality	adultery	abortion	euthanasia	disarm	racism
Czech	28%	32%	25%	35%	67%	53%
Slovenia	19%	32%	26%	30%	48%	37%
Hungary	38%	37%	45%	50%	58%	60%
Poland	40%	50%	59%	50%	49%	57%
Bulgaria	25%	40%	31%	40%	48%	44%

Table 3. Beliefs that the Church must engage in moral issues by country

	homosexuality	abortion	euthanasia	suicide
Czech	24%	34%	26%	12%
Slovenia	17%	34%	18%	12%
Hungary	16%	37%	27%	16%
Poland	6%	26%	8%	8%
Bulgaria	88%	60%	69%	82%
Lithuania	2%	20%	21%	7%
Latvia	7%	42%	41%	15%
Estonia	9%	42%	29%	13%

Table 4. Approval rate of what is commonly considered a sin

If we analyze the attitudes of Europeans towards moral issues set out in Table 3-4, with relative ease grasp the role the church should be an active combat, adjustment or reductions but the degree of involvement (according to the percentage assigned) differs depending on cultural and religious baggage, the individual countries.

Conclusions

Whenever a company reviews its history, he discovers that it has undergone an evolution, with ups and downs, with real progress or a setback. It is interesting to note what can happen when two big companies meet (Europe and South America, China or Africa), achieving relative nature of customs, institutions, values.

Sociology classic transition positivist theory developed in this relativism: *values are rooted in their substrate and social change with it*. They highlight the living conditions and interests; meet the same position in legal positivism, for which justice is closely related to morals.

Positivism that eliminates moral problem because it is not scientific.²⁶ If there is no absolute, no transcendent standard to discern good and evil, it is not possible to evaluate a social system than from our own value system and his own justification. We did not have no basis to consider the unacceptable actions of Hitler, of Stalin, Pol Pot or the apartheid regime.

This *relativism* was widespread and became a record; There is no truth, there is no objectivity, no absolute, neither universal nor fixed values. All notions are outdated, obsolete.

The plurality of concepts, ideologies, tastes, behavior and interpretations, induce the great majority of people the idea that all ideas and modes of action are available.

Also, moral and religious values have undergone many transformations and permutations of value over time, the fundamental categories by categories dormant or power or vice versa. The world's religions have been and still are important topics, ways of interpreting the world, and have influence in politics, economy, society as a whole. Communication between East and West was and still is difficult due to the great differences between cultures and people.

The debate around God "marked the decisive fate of the West"²⁷, a mystical devotion expressed from moment to moment, to rebellion against God. European culture is undoubtedly a culture marked by its depth reporting people to God. In the modern world, questioning autonomous reason legitimizing revelation, which does not want to obey blindly.

In the history, there have been two major religious currents, which has affected the entire civilization: Western religions and Eastern religions. The two fundamental systems were noted as forming values while sometimes acting in the same direction, sometimes in totally different directions.

If activity is leading Western spirit, creative individuality, modernity, oriental spirit which is in contrast, is characterized by passive resignation, fatalism, obedience, tradition. Thus, the dialogue becomes more difficult is heavily religious dialogue, since the differences between religions is essential.

Contemporary oriental religions, such as Buddhism, Hinduism, Brahmanism, Confucianism and the other Eastern religions, knowing the same values for moral and religious, all religions moralistic, focused on the concept of good practice, generosity, compassion, renunciation, patience, wisdom, etc.

The sixteenth century in Western Europe were recorded, on the one hand, intensification of trade and economic activity, and on the other hand, intensification of religious activities by the Reformation. This is apparently paradoxical, since the intensification of religious activity and increased economic activity are normally incompatible.

The experiences of many companies prove that increased religious activity is accompanied by a decrease of concerns for secular matters, and intensify economic activities is accompanied by a decrease in pietism or religious indifference. Companies that have embraced Protestantism did however exception to these historical regularities. It is interesting that in post-modernity and implicit in contemporary secularization is much more present in Protestant churches and less traditional, historic Catholic and Orthodox.

Immediately after 1989 in Central and Southeastern Europe, then in the former Soviet empire, contradictions morality worsened again, with aggravated immoral and amoral, both in the human behaviors individual and collective in the complex process of settlement moral values as human rights, honesty, generosity, respect other's property and life, compassion. They have also known and practiced. But education, family, social assistance was disturbed by privatization often associated with corruption, a lot of lying, slander, and then transformed into organized crime or deliberate violence exercised by gunmen on other people, deprived of weapons (terrorism). In this way, morality has become increasingly immoral and amoral because idealism its characteristic is not balanced by ethics appropriate by codes and rules, practice ethical, legal, political

and administrative to reduce the gap between what should be and what is man.²⁸

In the postwar period, Western European peoples affected by Nazism and fascism were able to remove both their non-values and those they germinated Eastern socialism. There was such a tendency for longer-term trend: the increasing influence of Western-style moral values worldwide. If activity is leading Western spirit, creative individuality, modernity, oriental spirit which is in contrast, is characterized by passive resignation, fatalism, obedience, tradition. Thus, the dialogue becomes unwieldy because religious values are very large differences.

NOTES

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⁴ The pew forum on religion & public life, *U.S. religious landscape survey* (2010), <http://religions.pewforum.org/affiliations> (Last accessed October 21, 2016)

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¹³ Max Weber, *Etica protestantă și spiritul capitalismului* (București: Editura Humanitas, 2003), 78.

¹⁴ Coman Andra Diana, *Societatea contemporană- între valoare și non-valoare* (27 Noiembrie 2010), <http://www.sighet-online.ro> (Last accessed October 1, 2016).

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¹⁶ Ibid., 258.

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¹⁸ Rezsóhazy, 122.

¹⁹ Virgil Ștefan Nițulescu, *Valorile tradiționale trebuie cunoscute, consemnate, conservate și protejate*, (02 Noiembrie 2011), <http://www.traditionalromanes.ro> (Last accessed September 6, 2016).

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²⁸ Tănase Sârbu, *Etică: valori și virtuți morale* (Iași: Editura Societății Academice „Matei Teiu Botez”, 2005), 91.